

Studies on N-Substituted Salicylhydroxamic Acid as Metal Complexing Ligand : Part V. N-Methyl Salicylhydroxamic Acid

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N-Methyl salicylhydroxamic acid (RH_2) and its Cu(II), Ni(II), Cd(II), Fe(III), Al(III), Ti(IV), V(V), and $UO_2(II)$ chelates have been isolated and magnetic properties of some of them have been studied. They are high spin complexes. Cu(II) is precipitated quantitatively as $Cu(RH)_2$ even in presence of Cd(II). On the basis of this quantitative separation, it is possible to detect Cd(II) in the centrifugate on centrifuging the precipitate $Cu(RH)_2$.

Some of the chelating properties of salicylhydroxamic acid were studied in our laboratory¹. More recently N-phenyl salicylhydroxamic acid has been prepared and the study of this compound as metal complexing ligand has yielded interesting results². It is therefore worthwhile to study the chelating properties of N-methyl derivative which may give more interesting results. With this in view N-methyl salicylhydroxamic acid (RH_2) has been isolated. By controlling pH the Cu(II), Cd(II), Ni(II), Fe(III), Al(III), Ti(IV), V(V), and $UO_2(II)$ chelates have been prepared. It has been observed that in some cases intense colouration takes place at lower pH values, most notable are Fe(III) and $UO_2(II)$ yielding purple and brown-red colouration respectively.

Cu(II) is found to be quantitatively precipitated as $Cu(RH)_2$ at pH 4.5-5.0, and may be weighed directly after drying at 110°. Cd(II) remains in solution under the specified condition. Cd(II) may be determined in the filtrate by precipitating as CdS followed by iodimetry. This quantitative separation may be utilised for detection of Cd(II) in presence of Cu(II). Cu(II) were precipitated with RH_2 , centrifuged and Cd(II) could be detected in the supernatant liquid by any classical method. A preliminary short notice has been published³.

EXPERIMENTAL

A. *Preparation of RH_2* : An aqueous solution (70 ml) containing N-methyl hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.1 mole) was taken in a conical flask (500 ml) and cooled in ice water. To this a concentrated, cold aqueous solution of KOH (0.1 mole) was added. Salicyl chloride (0.1 mole) and a further quantity of KOH (0.1 mole) were added slowly in portions alternately with vigorous stirring; pH of the solution was maintained at 10.5-11.0 for all the time. After shaking for a further period of two hours, pH of the solution was lowered to about 8

1. A. S. Bhaduri and N. N. Ghosh, *Z. anorg. allg. chem.*, 1958, **297**, 73; 1960, **303**, 117.
2. N. N. Ghosh and A. Bhattacharyya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **41**, 311; 1967, **44**, 972; 1968, **45**, 1103; 1970, **47**, 495.
3. N. N. Ghosh, A. Bhattacharyya and A. Bhattacharyya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 495.

by adding acetic acid. It was then extracted with ether and the clear aqueous layer was treated with CuSO_4 solution when a green copper compound separated. The compound was collected, suspended in small amount of water, cooled in ice and triturated with 9(N) H_2SO_4 —pH of the mixture should be near about 2. A white crystalline compound separated. The product obtained was further purified by dissolving in dilute ammonium hydroxide, treating with small amount of active charcoal and acidifying the resulting clear filtrate with 9(N) H_2SO_4 as before up to $\text{pH} \approx 2$. White crystalline compound separated was collected, washed with ice-cold water and dried in air. It melted at 136° . It is moderately soluble in water (0.856 g/100 g water at 30°) and soluble in acetone and ethanol. [Found : C, 57.81; H, 5.78; N, 8.26; $\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{O}_3\text{N}$ requires C, 57.48; H, 5.39; N, 8.38%].

B. *Preparation of metal chelates* : To a known amount of metal salt solution, an excess of the ligand dissolved in least amount of aqueous ammonia was added and the pH was adjusted to the required value. The precipitates obtained was washed thoroughly with water and air dried. They are insoluble in water and ethanol. Some properties along with the results of analyses are recorded in Table-I.

TABLE I
Analyses and properties of metal chelates

Compound	Colour	pH of pptn.	% Metal		% Nitrogen		% loss of water at 110°		Magnetic moment	
			Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	μ_{eff} in B.M.	Temp. in $^\circ\text{K}$
$\text{Cu}(\text{RH})_2$	Green	4.5—5.0	16.06	16.08	7.10	7.09			1.85	303
$\text{Cd}(\text{RH})_2$	White	6.5—7.0	25.11	25.29	6.40	6.30				
$\text{Ni}(\text{RH})_2$	Pale-green	6.6—6.8	14.90	15.03	7.21	7.16			3.24	304
$\text{Fe}(\text{RH})_3, 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Orange-red	2.0—2.5	9.18	9.19	6.71	6.90	9.19	8.88	5.88	304
$\text{Fe}(\text{RH})_3$	Orange-brown		10.05	10.08	7.70	7.57			5.97	304
$\text{Al}(\text{RH})_3, 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	White	4.0—4.5	4.97	4.67	7.27	7.26	10.80	10.30		
$\text{Al}(\text{RH})_3$	White		5.22	5.14	8.00	8.00				
$\text{TiO}(\text{RH})_2$	Yellow	6.6—7.0 (in presence of E.D.T.A.)	12.02	12.12	7.16	7.07				
$\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{RH})_2, \text{H}_2\text{O}$	Deep-violet	1.4—2.0	11.53	11.74	6.56	6.45	Decomposes		Dia	304
$\text{UO}_2(\text{RH})_2, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Orange-red	4.5—5.0	36.67	37.31	4.11	4.39	5.75	5.64		

Nitrogen was estimated by a modified Kjeldahl's method⁴ and magnetic susceptibilities were determined by the Guoy method. Diamagnetic corrections were made using Pascal's constants⁵. Magnetic data show that they are high spin complexes.

4. T. S. Ma, R. E. Lang and J. D. McKinley, *Micro. Chim. Acta.*, 1957, 368.

5. P. W. Selwood, *Magnetochemistry*, Interscience Publishers, New York, 1956.

C. *Quantitative separation of Cu(II) from Cd(II)*: Known volumes of 0.04564M copper nitrate and 0.05M cadmium nitrate solutions were taken and diluted to 75 ml with water. Free acid was neutralised with aqueous ammonia using methyl red indicator and dilute acetic acid was added until the colour just turned red. The solution was heated to 80° and 10 ml of 3.5% reagent in minimum volume of NH₄OH was added followed by 10 ml of ammonium acetate-acetic acid (1 : 1) buffer (0.2M). The precipitate was allowed to settle—filtered through a weighed sintered glass crucible (No. 4), washed four or five times with distilled water and dried at 110° to constant weight.

In the filtrate, Cd(II) was determined by precipitating as CdS and then iodimetry. The oxinate method yielded high results obviously due to co-precipitation of Cd(RH)₂. Results are stated in Table-II.

TABLE II

Separation of Cd(II) from Cu(II)

Total volume of the solution—100 ml

No. of Analyses*	Amount of Cu(II) in mg		Amount of Cd(II) in mg	
	Added	Separated	Added	Found
1.	11.6	11.5	—	—
2.	17.4	17.4	—	—
3.	23.2	23.2	—	—
4.	23.2	23.3	22.5	22.4
5.	23.2	23.1	33.9	33.6
6.	23.2	23.5	44.8	44.8
7.	51.0	50.5	11.7	11.8
8.	38.2	38.1	23.8	23.7
9.	12.8	12.6	71.7	71.1
10.	6.4	6.4	94.5	94.5

* Nos. 7-10 : 0.05014M Cu(II) nitrate and 0.05288M Cd(II) nitrate solutions were used.)

DISCUSSION

Magnetic susceptibility data are often useful in characterisation of the structure of many complex compounds⁵. Ni(RH)₂ is found to have $\mu_{eff} = 3.24$ B.M. showing that it is a high spin octahedral complex⁶. Value—1.85 B.M., obtained in the case of Cu(RH)₂ is on the normal range. Magnetic data of Fe(III) complexes indicate that they are octahedral outer orbital complexes. Vanadium compound is diamagnetic showing that vanadium has (d⁰) configuration and in the pentapositive state.

Results of analyses of the solutions containing Cu(II) and Cd(II) show that the separation is quantitative. On this basis, Cd(II) may be detected with aqueous hydrogen sulphide in the supernatant liquid after centrifuging the precipitate $\text{Cu}(\text{RH})_2$. Thus the classical method involving KCN may be avoided. The method of detection stated here, is simple and a rapid one. The limit of detection of Cd(II) is $5 \mu\text{g}$ and the concentration limit = 1 : 10,000. The tolerance limit of Cu(II) is found to be at least five times of Cd(II) present.

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